

Investigations on Lanthanum(III) and Yttrium(III) Chelates with Mordant Black Dyes

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The chromogenic reactions of lanthanum(III) and yttrium(III) with various mordant black dyes viz. 1-(1-hydroxy-2-naphthylazo)-6-nitro-2-naphthol-4-sulphonate (Eriochrome black T, abbr. Erio T), 1-(1-hydroxy-2-naphthylazo)-2-naphthol-4-sulphonate (Solochrome black 6BN, abbr. Solo 6BN) and 1-(1-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-phenylazo)-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid (Calmagite) have been investigated in aqueous media at 25° and ionic strength 0.1 M (NaClO₄). Composition and useful analytical parameters have been evaluated for the chelates. Stepwise formation constants have been determined potentiometrically using Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as used by Irving and Rossotti.

A number of *o,o'*-dihydroxyazo dyes (mordant black dyes) give interesting chromogenic reactions with metal ions. They have been extensively used in the detection, determination of microamounts of the metals and as metallochromic indicators in complexometric titrations. The important dyes of this group are Erio T, Solo 6BN and Calmagite. These ligands have been used as metallochromic indicators in complexometric titrations¹⁻⁵ and several metal chelates of these ligands⁶⁻¹³ have been investigated spectrophotometrically. Recently Mushran and coworkers¹⁴⁻¹⁷ have studied vanadium(IV), uranium(VI), indium(III), gallium(III), aluminium(III), molybdenum(VI) and tungsten(VI) chelates of these ligands spectrophotometrically and potentiometrically.

Experimental

Materials: The metal solutions were prepared by dissolving lanthanum chloride (E. Merck) and yttrium chloride (AR, BDH) in double distilled water and were estimated gravimetrically by precipitating metal oxalates and subsequent ignition and weighing as oxide. The solutions of required strength were then made by suitable dilution. The solutions of Erio T (Riedel, Germany), Calmagite (Fluka, Switzerland) were prepared by dissolving a weighed quantity in double distilled water. Solo 6BN (BDH, England) was dissolved in 10 per cent. ethanol. Sodium hydroxide, sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid solutions were prepared in double distilled water and were standardized by usual methods.

Instruments: A Leeds-Northrup pH meter with glass-calomel electrode assembly was used for pH measurements. The scale was standardized using L & N buffer supplied with the instrument. Absorbance measurements were made with a

Beckman DU spectrophotometer with 10 mm quartz cells.

Spectrophotometric studies

Conditions of Study

Instantaneous colour formation takes place when reagent and metal solutions are mixed at pH 8.5 to 9.8. The complexes were investigated at pH 8.5±0.1 (boric acid-borax buffer). The colour intensity remains constant even up to 24 hours. Addition of sodium perchlorate has no effect on absorbance. The ionic strength of the mixtures was maintained constant (0.1 M) with sodium perchlorate. The measurements were made at 25°.

Several mixtures containing different proportions of metal and reagent solutions were prepared and pH and ionic strength were fixed. The total volume of the mixtures was kept 25 ml. The absorption spectra were recorded from 400-600 nm. The Vosburgh and Cooper¹⁸ method (Fig. 1) showed formation of only one complex in each system. The λ_{\max} of Erio T, Solo 6BN and Calmagite are at 560, 570 and 570 nm respectively under the conditions of study. The λ_{\max} of lanthanum(III) and yttrium(III) chelates with the three reagents are 540, 530 and 520 nm respectively.

Composition of the Chelates

The composition ML₃ was established for the chelates. Similar results were obtained by applying continuous variation¹⁹, mole ratio²⁰ and straight line²¹ (Figs. 2 and 3) methods.

Analytical Applications

For the photometric determination of lanthanum(III) and yttrium(III) using these ligands,

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Fig. 1. Absorption spectra at pH 8.5.

A : Erio T ($8 \times 10^{-4} M$); B : La(III)-Erio T chelate ($C_M = 2.66 \times 10^{-4} M$; $C_R = 8 \times 10^{-4} M$); C : Y(III)-Erio T Chelate ($C_M = 2.66 \times 10^{-4} M$; $C_R = 8 \times 10^{-4} M$); D : Solo 6BN ($8 \times 10^{-4} M$); E : La(III)-Solo 6BN chelate ($C_M = 2.66 \times 10^{-4} M$; $C_R = 8 \times 10^{-4} M$); F : Y(III)-Solo 6BN chelate ($C_M = 2.66 \times 10^{-4} M$; $C_R = 8 \times 10^{-4} M$); G : Calmagite ($8 \times 10^{-4} M$); H : La(III)-Calmagite chelate ($C_M = 2.66 \times 10^{-4} M$; $C_R = 8 \times 10^{-4} M$); I : Y(III)-Calmagite chelate ($C_M = 2.66 \times 10^{-4} M$; $C_R = 8 \times 10^{-4} M$).

Fig. 2. Straight line plots at 520 nm in the excess of metal (pH=8.5).

$C_M = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$; $C_R = 4 \times 10^{-5} M$ (0.1-0.3 ml)
 A, B, C, La(III)-Erio T; A', B', C', Y(III)-Erio T;
 D, E, F, La(III)-Solo 6BN; D', E', F', Y(III)-Solo 6BN;
 G, H, I, La(III)-Calmagite; G', H', I', Y(III)-Calmagite.

important analytical parameters have been evaluated. These are given in Table 1.

TABLE-1 : BEER'S LAW, RINGBOM OPTIMUM RANGES AND SANDELL'S SENSITIVITY

System	Beer's law range (ppm)	Ringbom optimum range (ppm)	Sandell's sensitivity (γ/cm^2)
La(III)-Erio T	0.3-6.7	1.1-6.6	0.007
Y(III)-Erio T	0.2-4.3	1.0-4.2	0.004
La(III)-Solo 6BN	0.3-6.7	1.7-6.6	0.009
Y(III)-Solo 6BN	0.2-4.3	1.4-4.2	0.006
La(III)-Calmagite	0.3-6.7	2.2-6.6	0.005
Y(III)-Calmagite	0.2-4.3	1.4-4.2	0.003

The stability constants of metal-chelates have been computed by the continuous variation method. The values of log K for various systems are given in Table 2.

TABLE-2 : VALUES OF LOG K OF THE CHELATES

System	log K
La(III)-Erio T	13.01
Y(III)-Erio T	13.51
La(III)-Solo 6BN	13.92
Y(III)-Solo 6BN	14.42
La(III)-Calmagite	14.83
Y(III)-Calmagite	15.18

Potentiometric Studies

Bjerrum-Calvin^{23,24} pH-titration technique was adopted to investigate the chelates potentiometrically. Protonation constants and formation constants were computed by the method of Irving and Rossotti²⁵. The following mixtures were prepared :

(A) 5.0 ml NaClO₄ (1.0 M) and 5.0 ml HClO₄ (0.119 M).

(B) Mixture A and 25.0 ml Erio T or Solo 6BN or Calmagite (0.001 M).

(C) Mixture B and 5.0 ml LaCl₃ or YCl₃ solution (0.0002 M).

Total volume of above mixtures was made 50 ml by adding double distilled water. The mixtures were titrated against 0.3510 M NaOH. From the titration curves so obtained calculations of proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants were followed by the method of Irving and Rossotti²⁵. The values of \bar{n}_A (average number of protons associated with the ligand), \bar{n} (average number of ligands associated with the metal) and pL (free ligand exponent) were calculated. Protonation constants were evaluated from a plot between \bar{n}_A and pH. The values obtained are given in Table 3.

TABLE-3 : PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF THE LIGANDS $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄), Temp. 25°

Ligand	log K ₁ ^H	log K ₂ ^H	log β^H
Erio T	10.71	7.16	17.87
Solo 6BN	12.45	6.56	19.01
Calmagite	11.98	8.52	20.50

Fig. 3. Straight line plots at 520 nm in the excess of reagent ($pH=8.5$)
 $C_R=4 \times 10^{-3} M$; $C_M=4 \times 10^{-6} M$ (0.1-0.8 ml) A, B, C, La(III)-Erio T; A', B', C', Y(III)-Erio T;
 D, E, F, La(III)-Solo 6BN; D', E', F', Y(III)-Solo 6BN, G, H, I, La(III)-Calmagite, G', H', I',
 Y(III)-Calmagite.

The order of $\log \beta^H$ values, i.e., Calmagite > Solo 6BN > Erio T is of particular interest. The greater protonation constant of Solo 6BN than Erio T is attributed to the absence of $-NO_2$ group in Solo 6BN. Similarly, due to the presence of $-CH_3$ group in calmagite it has relatively greater protonation constant than Solo 6BN.

The stepwise formation constants were evaluated from the formation curves Fig. 4. Results are given in Table 4.

Fig. 4. Formation curves of the chelates.
 A=La(III)-Erio T; B=Y(III)-Erio T; C=La(III)-Solo 6BN, D=Y(III)-Solo 6BN; E=La(III)-Calmagite; F=Y(III)-Calmagite.

TABLE-4: FORMATION CONSTANTS OF THE CHELATES
 $\mu=0.1M$ ($NaClO_4$), Temp. 25°

System	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_3$	$\log \beta$
La(III)-Erio T	8.80	5.25	4.30	18.35
Y(III)-Erio T	10.70	9.17	5.35	25.22
La(III)-Solo 6BN	12.20	7.60	5.85	25.65
Y(III)-Solo 6BN	11.15	10.00	6.85	28.00
La(III)-Calmagite	14.60	7.50	6.07	28.17
Y(III)-Calmagite	15.70	7.85	5.90	29.45

It can be seen that $\log \beta$ values lie in the order Y(III)-Calmagite > La(III)-Calmagite > Y(III)-Solo 6BN > La(III)-Solo 6BN > Y(III)-Erio T > La(III)-Erio T. Thus overall formation constants ($\log \beta$) of above metal chelates follow the same order with respect to ligands as the protonation constants of the ligands. However order of $\log \beta$ for a specific ligand is always Y(III)-chelate > La(III)-chelate.

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